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MODERN ASPECTS OF THE ETIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS OF ORAL CAVITY FLOOR PHLEGMON

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Phlegmon of the oral cavity floor is an acute purulent disease characterized by the combined involvement of several anatomical spaces in the maxillofacial region, namely: the sublingual, submandibular, and mental triangle areas. According to statistical data, the prevalence of this pathology is 20-30% among patients admitted for inpatient treatment.

Despite numerous studies, the issue of treating odontogenic phlegmons of the oral cavity floor remains relevant. This is due to the following factors: increasing antibiotic resistance of microorganisms and the risk of rapid spread of the inflammatory process.

The danger of oral cavity floor phlegmon lies in its tendency to rapidly spread through fascial spaces, along the vessels of the neck, pharynx, esophagus, and mediastinum. It is accompanied by disruption of microcirculation and neurotrophic processes, which contributes to rapid generalization of infection and, consequently, severe complications [8]. The mortality rate among this category of patients remains consistently high, ranging from 20% to 60%.

The main cause of such phlegmons is odontogenic infection of the oral cavity.

According to various studies, the causes of infection spread in perioral phlegmons include infections from apical foci during exacerbation of chronic periodontitis, less frequently in acute periodontitis, as well as during difficult eruption of the lower wisdom tooth, suppurated radicular cyst, infection of the extracted tooth socket, and exacerbation of periodontal diseases. Additionally, acute and chronic odontogenic osteomyelitis and acute periostitis of the jaw can trigger the development of phlegmons in the maxillofacial region and neck.

Such phlegmons most often occur in young people aged 20 to 30, which is associated with the highest intensity of dental caries and difficulties in the eruption of the lower eighth molar. However, in recent years, the number of elderly patients suffering from diabetes mellitus has also increased, against which background the generalization of the purulent-inflammatory process is more frequently observed.

Various authors note the deterioration of dental care in remote areas and rural localities. This is related to unsatisfactory prevention and educational work with the population, as well as an increase in the proportion of patients with immunodeficiency conditions.

Additionally, causes of phlegmon development can include tonsillar sources, namely purulent-inflammatory processes in the palatine tonsils; head and neck injuries with damage to soft tissues and bones; and injuries to the pharynx, esophagus, and larynx, including iatrogenic ones.

Besides the main sources of the purulent-inflammatory process, it is also necessary to note the presence of underlying pathologies in patients, which negatively affect the course of the condition. According to data, surgical sepsis most often developed in patients with a complicated medical history and concomitant diseases. Among the 283 patients described by this author, 55.2% of surgical sepsis cases had an odontogenic nature, 22.5% of patients had adenophlegmons, 12.4% had complicated infected wounds of the head and neck, and 9.9% had complicated furuncles and carbuncles of the face.

The evolution of microflora causing oral cavity floor and neck phlegmons is traced in the literature, depending on the year of publication and the microbiological methods used by the authors. It is noted that previously, staphylococci held "primacy" among the pathogens of perimandibular phlegmons, with their proportion reaching 69%.

Subsequently, streptococci, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and other microorganisms, as well as their associations, were cultured more frequently.

In recent years, when studying the etiology of surgical infections in general and purulent-inflammatory lesions of the head and neck in particular, increasing attention has been given to anaerobes. It has long been known that the main habitat of anaerobes is the digestive tract, where there are no sterile sections at all, and anaerobes constitute a significant portion of the microbial landscape in surgical infections etiologically and anatomically related to the floor of the oral cavity and neck. Aedinova I.V. et al. (2020) identified polymicrobial associations including *F. nucleatum*, *Bacteroides* spp., and *Peptostreptococcus* spp. in putrid-necrotic phlegmon of the oral cavity floor.

Loose connective tissue is predominantly affected in the subcutaneous interfascial, intermuscular, paravascular, and paraneural tissues, as well as around the organs of the oral cavity and neck. The relatively free communication between the spaces of the oral cavity floor and neck, along with the topography of fasciae, vessels, and nerves, anatomically predispose the area to the spread of infection via contact descending pathways up to the mediastinum, potentially leading to mediastinitis. Additionally, the peculiarities of blood supply and structural interrelationships of the maxillofacial region and the brain create the possibility for ascending spread of the purulent-inflammatory process, potentially transitioning into purulent-septic thrombophlebitis of the facial veins, sinus thrombosis, purulent meningitis, encephalitis, and intracranial abscess.

Thus, analysis of available literature shows that, despite the achievements of modern medicine, the problems of etiology and pathogenesis of oral cavity floor phlegmons remain relevant.